

Rotatory Powers of Some Disubstituted Camphoranilic Acids.

BY MAHAN SINGH AND BIKRAM SINGH.

The work on disubstituted camphoranilic acids (*J. Chem. Soc.*, 1931, 478; *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1932, 9, 363) has been further extended to include methyl chlorocamphoranilic acids.

The rotatory powers of 2'-methyl-5'-chloro-, 2'-methyl-4'-chloro-, 2'-methyl-3'-chloro-, 4'-methyl-2'-chloro- and 2'-methoxy-4'-chloro-camphoranilic acids have been determined in four solvents, methyl alcohol, ethyl alcohol, acetone and methyl ethyl ketone for two wave-lengths, Hg_{5780} and Hg_{5461} . The mercury violet is rather dim and, therefore, the rotatory powers could not be measured in all the cases.

The following tables record the molecular rotatory powers of methylchlorocamphoranilic acids, methylcamphoranilic acids and chlorocamphoranilic acids.

TABLE I.

(M) Hg_{5780}

	2'-Methyl 5'-chloro-.	2'-Methyl- 4'-chloro-.	2'-Methyl- 3'-chloro-.	4'-Methyl- 2'-chloro-.
MeOH	211·8	174·7	145·5	76·3
EtOH	210·3	165·0	142·3	56·6
Me ₂ CO	132·5	124·6	66·2	Almost nil
MeEtCO	166·6	129·4	89·0	10·1

TABLE II.

(M) Hg_{5780}

	o-Me.	m-Me.	p-Me.	o-Cl.	m-Cl.	p-Cl
MeOH	144·5	137·3	162·6	54·1	147·0	166·3
EtOH	127·2	121·3	137·3	30·9	119·2	142·3
Me ₂ CO	88·1	93·9	98·2	-21·4	100·5	126·9
MeEtCO	104·7	108·3	137·3	-10·2	131·5	148·6

It will be seen from the study of the tables that the introduction of a chlorine atom in the first three cases leads to the enhancement of rotation, the maximum effect being when the methyl and the chlorine, both of similar polarity, are in the *para* position with respect to one another. The effect is the least when the two groups are present in the *ortho* position with respect to one another. In the 4th compound the chlorine atom is present in the *ortho* position with respect to the substituted amino group. There is a very great fall in the rotation of the original compound; in methyl alcohol from 162° to 76° and in ethyl alcohol from 137.3° to 56.6° . This fall in the rotatory power is very marked in the ketonic solvents; in acetone the fall is from 98.0° to almost zero, and in methyl ethyl ketone from 137° to 10° . 2'-Chloro-4'-methylcamphoranilic acid was examined in acetone in a very concentrated solution and the difference between the solvent and the solution readings were so small as to be within the experimental error. It has been shown by Singh and Singh in the case of *o*-chlorocamphoranilic acid (*J. Chem. Soc.*, 1927, 1994. *cf.* also experimental), and by Forster and Spinner (*J. Chem. Soc.*, 1919, 115, 889), in the case of *o*-chlorophenylimino-camphor that chlorine in the *ortho* position has a great depressing effect on the rotatory power of the original compound.

The question may be looked at from the point of view of the introduction of the methyl group. In the first three cases the methyl group enters into the *ortho* position with respect to the substituted amino group, so that it is in close proximity to the optically active group. It is, therefore, reasonable to suppose that it will exert a uniform influence on the chlorocamphoranilic acids. It increases the rotatory power considerably when it goes in to the *para* position with respect to the chlorine atom. It has very little effect when it is in the *meta* position with respect to the chlorine, but when present in the *ortho* position with regard to the chlorine atom, it has some depressing influence in the ketonic solvents.

In the 4th compound the methyl group is present in the 4'-position and it has raised the rotations of 2'-chlorocamphoranilic acid to a small extent.

A methoxy group in the 2'-position is also known to have a depressing effect (Singh and Singh, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1930, 1301; *cf.* also Rule and others, *ibid.*, 1928, 1493), In 2'-methoxy-4'-chlorocamphoranilic acid the rotatory powers are lower than those of the 4'-chlorocamphoranilic acid in all the solvents examined.

Influence of the solvent on the rotatory power.—The solvents employed in the decreasing order of their dielectric constants are methyl alcohol, ethyl alcohol, acetone, ethyl methyl ketone. A reference to the tables will show that the sequences of solvents in order of decreasing or increasing rotatory power is the same as their dielectric constants except that the position of ethyl methyl ketone and acetone is reversed. But this regularity does not extend to 3'-chlorocamphoranilic acids and 4'-chlorocamphoranilic acid, where the sequence of ethyl methyl ketone and ethyl alcohol is also reversed.

EXPERIMENTAL.

Condensation of camphoric anhydride with chlorotoluidines and chloroanisidine.—Camphoric anhydride and the amine (equimol.) were heated together with fused sodium acetate at 140–50° for 3-4 hours. The product was dissolved in alcohol and precipitated with water, when a brown mass came down. It was extracted with a dilute solution of caustic soda or ammonia to remove any imide. The filtered solution was then acidified with dilute hydrochloric acid. The white solid thus obtained was recrystallised from alcohol (charcoal).

2'-Methyl-5'-chlorocamphoranilic acid crystallised from alcohol in needles, m.p. 206°. It is soluble in the usual organic solvents. (Found: N, 4.5; Equiv., 322.5. $C_{17}H_{22}O_3NCl$ requires N, 4.3 per cent. Equiv., 322.5).

2'-Methyl-4'-chlorocamphoranilic acid crystallised from alcohol in silky needles, m.p. 221–22°. It is readily soluble in acetone and benzene and less readily in methyl alcohol and ethyl alcohol. (Found: N, 4.5; Equiv., 323. $C_{17}H_{22}O_3NCl$ requires N, 4.3 per cent. Equiv. 323.5).

2'-Methyl-3'-chlorocamphoranilic acid separated from alcohol in a crystalline mass, m.p. 219°. The quantity of the imide formed is appreciable in this case but no attempt was made to purify and analyse the compound. (Found: N, 4.50; Equiv., 325. $C_{17}H_{22}O_3NCl$ requires N, 4.3 per cent. Equiv., 323.5).

4'-Methyl-2'-chlorocamphoranilic acid crystallised from alcohol in needles, m.p. 206–07°. The yield of the acid is not so good as in the first three cases. The acid is readily soluble in ketone, less readily in alcohols. (Found: N, 4.55; Equiv., 323. $C_{17}H_{22}O_3NCl$ requires N, 4.3 per cent. Equiv., 323.5).

2-Methoxy-5-chlorocamphoranilic acid was obtained as a micro-crystalline mass, m.p. 176-77°, yield about 10%. It is soluble in the usual organic solvents. (Found: N, 4.3; Equiv., 339.5. $C_{17}H_{22}O_4NCl$ requires N, 4.12 per cent. Equiv., 339.5).

2', 3' and 4'-Methylcamphoranilic acids and 2', 3', 4'-chlorocamphoranilic acids were prepared by the general method given above. The rotatory powers of these compounds have been determined for sodium light by Singh and Puri (*J. Chem. Soc.*, 1926, 504) and Singh and Singh (*loc. cit.*). The rotatory powers of these compounds have now been determined for two wave-lengths, namely Hg_{5780} and Hg_{5461} .

TABLE III.

Solvent.	Conc. (g./25 c.c.).	Hg_{5780} α.	Hg_{5461} α.	Hg_{4358} α.
<i>2'-Methyl-5'-chlorocamphoranilic acid.</i>				
MeOH	0.2500	65.5	75.5	...
EtOH		65.0	74.5	112.5
Me ₂ CO		41.0	50.5	97.5
MeCOEt		51.5	63.0	...
<i>2'-Methyl-4'-chlorocamphoranilic acid.</i>				
MeOH	0.2500	54.0	63.0	105.0
EtOH		51.0	59.0	103.0
Me ₂ CO		38.5	45.5	...
MeCOEt	0.2000	40.0	47.0	...
<i>2'-Methyl-3'-chlorocamphoranilic acid.</i>				
MeOH	0.2500	45.0	52.5	96.5
EtOH		44.0	51.0	91.0
Me ₂ CO		20.5	30.5	...
MeCOEt	0.2000	27.5	40.0	...
<i>4'-Methyl-2'-chlorocamphoranilic acid.</i>				
MeOH	0.2500	23.5	32.5	36.0
EtOH	..	17.5	24.5	35.0
Me ₂ CO	0.4000
MeCOEt	..	3.3	4.4	...

Solvent.	Conc. (g./25 c.c.).	H_{5780}^{α}	H_{5461}^{α}	H_{4358}^{α}
<i>2'-Methoxy-5'-chlorocamphoranilic acid.</i>				
MeOH	0.2500	38.0	45.0	...
EtOH	..	30.0	36.0	57.5
Me ₂ CO	0.3000	18.0	22.0	...
MeCOEt	..	19.37	23.79	...

TABLE IV.

	H_{5780}^{α}	H_{5461}^{α}	H_{5780}^{α}	H_{5461}^{α}	H_{4358}^{α}
<i>2'-Methylcamphoranilic acid.</i>			<i>2'-Chlorocamphoranilic acid.</i>		
Conc. = 0.2000 (g./25 c.c.).			Conc. = 0.3000 (g./25 c.c.).		
MeOH	50.0	65.0	17.5	21.0	35.0
EtOH	44.0	55.0	10.0	12.0	17.5
Me ₂ CO	28.75	36.6	-6.9	-8.3	...
MeCOEt	36.25	45.8	-3.3	-4.0	...
<i>3'-Methylcamphoranilic acid.</i>			<i>3'-Chlorocamphoranilic acid.</i>		
Conc. = 0.2000 (g./25 c.c.).			Conc. = 0.2500 (g./25 c.c.).		
MeOH	47.5	62.5	47.5	62.5	...
EtOH	42.0	54.0	38.5	48.0	85.0
MeCO	32.5	42.4	32.5	40.0	...
MeCOEt	37.5	48.3	42.5	52.5	...
<i>4'-Methylcamphoranilic acid.</i>			<i>4'-Chlorocamphoranilic acid.</i>		
Conc. = 0.2000 (g./25 c.c.).			Conc. = 0.2500 (g./25 c.c.).		
MeOH	56.25	70.0	53.75	71.75	158.5
EtOH	47.5	57.5	46.0	59.0	105.0
MeCO	34.0	42.0	41.0	51.5	...
MeCOEt	47.5	57.5	48.0	62.5	...

The rotatory powers were determined in a 2-dcm. tube.

